

UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE (UAV) IN CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT: A LITERATURE REVIEW, APPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of the article is to analyze the current directions of UAV application areas in the management of processes in construction, limitations and development opportunities, considering the fusion between academic publications and practical ones.*

Methodology/approach – *This research puts forward a bibliographic synthesis to summarize the results of 20 research papers published in 2012-2020 and highlights the growing trend of using UAVs in the construction sector.*

Findings – *The UAV is widely used in structural condition assessment, occupational health and safety, quantity survey and logistics activities. Cost and time efficiency are the primary benefits for using UAV in construction processes. Multi-rotor is the most common structure of UAV and a multitude of sensors can be attached to the UAV such as digital camera, thermal and infrared sensor. The control of the UAVs can be manual or a pre-programmed flight.*

Research limitations/implications – *The research limitations are related to the methodological approach which consists of identifying the scientific papers based on keywords in academic databases.*

Originality/value – *This paper outlines the classification of UAV applications in construction research and pleads the use of applications in construction quality control along the project implementation.*

Key words: UAV, construction quality management.

Introduction

The current breakthrough in the construction field makes use of the integration of data digitization, robotization and the application of modern technologies on quality controlling of the structures and on checking the project implementation.

In the field of aeronautics, unmanned aircraft vehicles (UAVs), also known as "drones", are considered a modern and innovative technology in both military and civilian fields.

By analogy with other industries, the application of UAV technology is to be found in the field of Architecture Engineering and Construction (AEC) and generates a considerable potential of use in various fields such as:

- structural condition assessment,
- management of logistics activities,
- occupational health and safety management,
- assembly of construction elements,
- verifying the progress of the works, and etc.

Research methodology

The multitude of the UAV technology applications in the field of construction has been of relatively high interest since 2012. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the current directions of application areas, limitations and development opportunities, considering the fusion of academic publications with practical ones, and also of legislative regulations in force.

The objectives of the bibliographic synthesis

This paper aims at the following:

1. to identify the State-of-the-Art of UAV technology applications in the AEC,
2. to acknowledge methodologies applied in the management of construction projects,
3. to identify limitations and research opportunities in the management of construction projects.

Identifying the academic sources

Identifying academic sources was based on keywords, such as "UAV", "drone", "unmanned aerial vehicle", "quality management", in academic database Scopus.

Following the collection of scientific articles in individual publisher databases such as Elsevier, their summary and keywords were analyzed individually. The large number of publications required the creation of a complex database, containing data on the journal and year of publication, keywords used and the rate of citations, which points out their relevance.

The current stage of the application of UAV technology in AEC

The bibliographic synthesis consists of 20 scientific articles published in 2012-2020, represented in graphic form in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Frequency of publication of scientific articles in the period 2012-2020 with regard to UAV application

Of the 20 academic sources studied, 18 articles present UAV applications in the field of AEC and two present the State-of-the-Art of UAV application.

The applications in AEC are made up of a multitude of subdomains. The distribution by categories of the 18 scientific publications is represented in Table 1.

Table 1: Applicability of UAV technology in AEC

Applications of UAV technology	Reference
Topography	(Agüera-Vega et al., 2018)
Logistics management of construction sites	(Guo et al., 2020)
Progress management of construction processes	(Zollmann et al., 2014; Braun & Borrmann, 2019)
Quantity survey	(Siebert & Teizer, 2014; Jeong et al., 2020)
Risk management of construction sites	(Melo et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019)
Structural condition assessment	(Dobson et al., 2013; Hallermann & Morgenthal, 2013; Hallermann et al., 2014; Sankarasrinivasan et al., 2015; Ellenberg et al., 2016; Hallermann & Morgenthal, 2016; Seo et al., 2018)
Natural hazards	(D'Oleire-Oltmanns et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2020)

Seo et al. (2018) presented the efficiency of structural flaw inspection, analyzing images taken by UAV and compared the results with a technical report prepared by the US Department of Transportation that considers manual (traditional) inspection of the same objective.

Hallermann and Morgenthal (2016) put forward the computerized processing of the images taken after the inspection and the generation of the 3D georeferenced digital model with the accuracy of approximately five millimeters.

Real-time investigation of cracks detection and assessment of surface degradation by integrating image processing algorithms following the UAV inspection is presented in the study by Sankarasrinivasan et al. (2015).

The study by Hallermann et al. (2014) highlighted the efficiency of the UAV inspection which aimed to detect the relative displacements of a 180-m-long retaining wall section in less than eight minutes.

Melo et al. (2017) identified the potential of UAV inspection to improve human resource pattern of behavior and reduce the risk associated with occupational health and safety. Processing images by the means of artificial intelligence offered the chance to identify the risk in the vicinity of construction equipment (Kim et al., 2019).

Methods of verifying the progress of construction activities are presented in the study by Zollmann et al. (2014), which supported the application of augmented reality and digital reconstruction, by processing images taken by a drone. In a recent study, Guo et al. (2020) showed the possibility to identify construction equipment, such as excavators, trucks, concrete mixers, concrete cranes, in different locations on the site.

The complex analysis of large excavation volumes by processing UAV recorded images of high-speed railway infrastructure construction project, generated low costs compared to alternative scanning methods and facilitated the decision-making process of the project manager (Siebert and Teizer, 2014).

The current synthesis of the exclusive application of UAV in construction processes and structural condition assessment are presented in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: Uses of UAVs in construction processes

Domain of applicability	Method	Reference
Logistics management on site	Automatic image processing by deep learning algorithms	(Guo et al., 2020)
Occupational health and safety management	Visual analysis	(Melo et al., 2017)
	Merger of UAV inspection with dynamic BIM	(Liu et al., 2019)
Dimensional measurements	Image processing by artificial intelligence	(Kim et al., 2019)
	Generating a high-resolution 3D model	(Jeong et al., 2020)
Three-dimensional measurements	Generating high-resolution 3D model	(Siebert & Teizer, 2014)
Topography	Generating cross sections by applying an automatic algorithm to the point clouds	(Agüera-Vega et al., 2018)
Checking the progress of the works	The fusion of digital reconstruction and augmented reality	(Zollmann et al., 2014)
	The fusion of BIM and inverse photogrammetry process	(Braun & Borrmann, 2019)

Table 3: Uses of UAVs structural condition assessment

Domain of applicability	Method	Reference
Structural condition assessment	• displacement detection	• generating a high-resolution 3D model (Hallermann et al., 2014)
	• cracks detection	• combining methods hat and HSV (Sankarasrinivasan et al., 2015)
		• generating a high-resolution 3D model (Hallermann & Morgenthal, 2016)
	• infrastructure (roads)	• generating a high-resolution 3D model (Dobson et al., 2013)
	• infrastructure (bridges)	• automatically detection of the position and the structural non-conformities (Ellenberg et al., 2016)
Natural hazard	• landslides	• generating the digital elevation model (DEM) (Wang et al., 2020)
	• river erosion	• generating the digital terrain model (DTM) and orthophotographs (D'Oleire-Oltmanns et al., 2012)

Methodologies applied in the management of construction processes

The UAV inspection methodology consists of the following stages 1) defining the flight parameters of the drone, 2) data acquisition, and 3) data processing.

UAV types, sensors, and flight parameters

The studied scientific articles present two types of UAV structure: fixed wing and multi-rotor. A multitude of sensors can be attached to the UAV such as digital camera, thermal and infrared sensor.

Another important parameter is the flying height or distance from the object of interest.

Data acquisition

The main component of the UAV is the Flight Control Unit (FCU). This hardware component processes and implements not only the commands transmitted by the pilot but also the pre-programmed flight via GPS way points.

Data processing

A major topic of interest in research is the improvement and development of efficient image processing techniques. The studied articles present four categories of image processing in construction management, based on the time of data processing. Three of them (the visual analysis, the photogrammetric methods, and the methods of the artificial vision algorithms) are validated in the post-inspection processing of the images taken by UAV, while the computed algorithms may be used for real-time results.

Possibilities of UAV integration in construction quality management

Following the undertaken research, the authors advocate for the application of UAV in construction quality management, during the design, construction and operating stages.

Design stage

The environmental factors that may affect the mechanical strength and structural stability of the construction project can be evaluated by using the high-resolution 3D model and geotechnical studies. The integration of the digital terrain model, resulted after UAV images processing, in Building Information Modeling (BIM) models can contribute to the improvement of the geospatial visualization and complement the information on the construction surrounding environment. The UAV inspection can facilitate decision-making with regard to the interdisciplinary coordination and optimization of the technical design solutions.

Construction stage

The quality control during the construction stage requires daily records, which are extremely time-consuming and a lot of human resource is needed. Usually, the quality control of the activities is completed by various types of reports or protocols and the traceability is performed manually. In this context, data traceability leads to difficult identification of the history and low precision in pinpointing activities.

The UAV inspection presents high applicability in the quality control of construction activities, due to time and economic efficiency compared to conventional tools, high precision of the collected data and the possibility to store it in an integrated digital platform.

The authors propose the use of BIM models when performing quality control. The process involves comparing the 3D model with the digital reconstruction resulted from the UAV inspection, in activities such as verifying:

- The geometric parameters of earthworks and foundation works;
- The alignment of formworks and the position of reinforcements in concrete elements;
- The structural non-conformities inside concrete elements (local gaps, reinforcements position);
- The joints of precast concrete elements;

Furthermore, the UAV can improve the documentation of works that become hidden.

Operating stage

Conventional inspections involve complex and expensive procedures such as the use of access platforms or special scaffolding. The main advantage of drone inspection is the flexibility to record data related to structures located in hard-to-reach areas as well as high altitudes such as dams, bridges, or wind turbines.

Structural health monitoring and extension of a structure's life span through periodic inspections are of economic, social, and environmental protection interest.

Limitations and research opportunities

The increase in the applicability of large-scale UAV in the civil field is conditioned by preliminary considerations: technological limitations for the ability to maneuver autonomously, in safe conditions and the adaptation of the legal requirements for operation and surveillance during the flight (Floreano and Wood, 2015).

UAV endurance, autonomy and maneuverability

The study by Otto et al. (2018) identified the influencing factors of drone endurance: 1) drone structure, 2) flight altitude, 3) take-off speed, 4) payload, 5) meteorological conditions.

A large part of inspection applications considers pre-programming the flight path using GPS waypoints but in the case of inspections inside buildings, pre-programming of the trajectory is not possible due to the limitations of the GPS signal.

Legislative norms and regulations

The socio-economic potential of using UAV in the civil field requires both technological advances and the framework of legal regulations to allow functionality in conditions of safety, confidentiality, and security.

The study by Dobson et al. (2013) indicated the need to facilitate the obtaining of the flying license. Hallermann and Morgenthal (2013) specified the adaptation of the regulations regarding the autonomous control of the UAV in Germany. Taking into account the safety conditions, the authors indicated that the pilot must maintain the Visual Line of Sight Operation throughout the inspection.

Conclusions

The article is a synthesis of 20 bibliographic sources related to the applicability of UAV in AEC and highlights the growing trend of using this technology in construction quality management, occupational health and safety management, and progress monitoring of construction activities. Although UAV does not tend to replace current technologies, their usefulness can supplement and complement the existing ones.

The topic of a new research is monitoring an excavation of roughly 28 meters in depth, executed for building a multi-storey commercial complex which was abandoned after the basement completion. The construction site forms a rectangle of approximately 10,000 square meters.

The new research is conducted within the framework of the project "*Monitoring the construction site located at 62B Traian Street*", County of Constanta, Romania and involves long term (numerous years) assessment of the soil displacements using UAV.

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